

Bibliothecarius Modernus: AI-Assisted Translation Infrastructure for Latin Patristic Literature

Ryan Wolfslayer, MSLIS

Library Systems Developer

ORCID: 0000-0001-8914-9706

Version 1.0 | December 2025

Abstract

Latin patristic literature spans fifteen centuries of Christian thought, yet much of it remains inaccessible to modern readers. Traditional translation economics have created a self-reinforcing canon: popular authors receive multiple translations while large bodies of work remain locked behind a language barrier that few contemporary readers can cross. This paper describes Bibliothecarius Modernus, a project applying library science principles and AI-assisted workflows to systematically address this access problem. The project implements a state machine architecture that orchestrates multiple AI systems (deep research, translation, text-to-speech, video composition) while maintaining human oversight at critical decision points. Since its public launch in June 2024, the project has produced more than 200 translations distributed across YouTube, a Jekyll-based blog with parallel Latin/English display, Archive.org, GitHub, and Zenodo with persistent DOI identifiers. This paper documents the project's philosophy, technical architecture, quality mechanisms, and the generalizable principles that emerged from building reliable agentic workflows.

1. Introduction: The Access Problem

Latin Christian literature represents one of the largest bodies of intellectually significant text that remains effectively inaccessible to most readers. The *Patrologia Latina* alone, a 19th-century compilation that makes no claim to completeness, spans 221 volumes containing works from the 3rd through 13th centuries. Beyond canonical figures like Augustine, Jerome, and Gregory the Great, these volumes contain thousands of texts by authors whose names appear in no popular bibliography: letters about parish administration, disputations on monastic practice, hagiographies of local saints, cosmological speculation, church council proceedings.

Much of this material has never been translated into English. Where translations exist, they often appear in expensive academic editions, out-of-print volumes, or Victorian-era prose that creates its own comprehension barrier. The economics are straightforward: human translation is labor-intensive, academic incentive structures reward original research over translation work, and publishers cannot justify investment in translations with uncertain audiences. The predictable result is a self-reinforcing canon where translated texts receive attention, generating demand for more translations of the same authors, while untranslated texts remain invisible.

This is an information access problem. The texts exist. They have been digitized. They sit in databases that anyone can download. But for readers who do not command Latin (which is to say, nearly all readers) these texts might as well not exist.

Bibliothecarius Modernus launched publicly on June 20, 2024, with a translation of Fulgentius of Ruspe's *De Fide ad Petrum*. The project emerged from a convergence of factors: nearly a decade of professional experience building library systems that solve access problems, a

personal interest in Latin patristic literature, and the recognition that AI had made this particular access barrier tractable in a way it had not been before. The first translation, the *Libri Carolini* produced in May 2024 for personal use, demonstrated what was now possible. A text that would have required either substantial Latin expertise or expensive academic editions became readable in an afternoon. The librarian's instinct followed naturally: if this access problem could be solved for one person, it should be solved for anyone interested.

2. Project Philosophy

2.1 Library Values as Operating Principles

The project applies library science principles to a specific access problem rather than approaching it as scholarship, ministry, or content creation.

Collection development. The project operates under a defined scope: Latin patristic texts lacking accessible English versions, with preference for works without existing translations or where translations are locked in expensive or out-of-print editions. This boundary ensures coherence while allowing flexibility for occasional exceptions when personal interest or user requests warrant inclusion of better-known texts.

Language constraint. The collection focuses exclusively on Latin texts. My limited but functional Latin allows basic evaluation of translation quality, catching obvious errors and verifying that output makes sense against the source. Greek, Coptic, or Syriac texts would require translating blind, without capacity to detect when AI produces nonsense. The constraint is practical, not arbitrary.

Source pragmatism. The *Patrologia Latina* serves as the primary source collection. Scholars may note that these 19th-century editions do not always represent the best available manuscripts. But the *Patrologia Latina* offers machine-readable text through Archive.org, making it practically accessible in a way that superior critical editions often are not. The tradeoff between textual perfection and actual accessibility resolves in favor of accessibility.

Serendipitous discovery. Rather than organizing content topically or systematically, releases follow a deliberately meandering path through the collection. This approach mirrors what library scholars have identified as a key benefit of browsable collections: the encounter with unexpected material that directed search cannot surface. Each text receives its moment of visibility, and viewers may discover works they would never have sought deliberately. A sixth-century letter about parish administration appears alongside major theological treatises, each given equivalent presentation.

2.2 Translation Philosophy

The project treats AI as a sophisticated tool requiring transparency rather than as a co-author or autonomous agent.

Human responsibility. I remain responsible for text selection, curatorial decisions, translation direction, quality review, and all editorial choices. AI performs translation under human prompting and oversight. The distinction matters for accountability: errors in translation reflect tool limitations and human review failures, not autonomous AI decisions.

Transparency as default. Every output discloses AI involvement. Viewers and readers approach the content knowing translations are machine-generated with human oversight, not scholarly editions produced through traditional methods. This calibrates expectations appropriately.

Verification infrastructure. Videos display original Latin alongside English translation. The blog provides parallel Latin/English views with synchronized chunk numbering. Anyone with Latin reading ability can check the work. This transparency serves both accountability and education.

Depth as a later stage. The project positions itself as an entry point rather than a destination. Translations are good enough for survey, engagement, and discovery. They allow readers to encounter ideas, identify what interests them, and form preliminary understanding. They do not replace critical editions, scholarly apparatus, or careful study of primary languages. The explicit encouragement: if something sparks interest, pursue it further.

2.3 Long-Tail Assumptions

The project operates on long-tail assumptions. Massive breakout success is neither expected nor required. The goal is connecting individual texts with the specific people who would find them valuable: a researcher working on a narrow topic, a pastor preparing a sermon series, a curious reader following an unexpected thread. One text reaching one person who could not otherwise have accessed it justifies the translation.

This represents a genuine expansion of what is practically available, not merely faster production of the same things that would have been translated anyway. Under traditional economics, translation labor determines what gets translated. Popular authors with established audiences justify the investment. Obscure texts with uncertain demand do not. Removing the labor constraint changes the calculus. A letter about purchasing hogs for a parish can be translated, researched, and published. The effort required no longer filters for expected audience size.

3. Technical Architecture

3.1 The Core Problem: Making Probabilistic Systems Deterministic

AI agents are inherently probabilistic. Given identical instructions, they produce different results across sessions: they forget context, skip steps, and reinterpret guidelines. For a multi-hour workflow spanning multiple sessions, this unpredictability becomes unworkable.

In this context, an *agent* refers to a large language model operating with tool-use capabilities, able to read and write files, execute scripts, and make sequential decisions toward a goal. Unlike a simple chatbot that responds to single queries, an agent persists across multiple actions and maintains (or attempts to maintain) coherent state toward an objective.

The Bibliothecarius Modernus architecture addresses agent unpredictability through structural constraints rather than better prompting. The agent does not remember what to do next; it reads its current state from a canonical file and executes the appropriate action. The system makes correct behavior the path of least resistance and incorrect behavior structurally difficult.

3.2 State Machine Architecture

The pipeline implements a formal state machine with defined states. Each project maintains a single canonical state file that records current state, accumulated metadata, file paths, costs, and timestamped notes.

Figure 1 presents the high-level system architecture, showing how source materials flow through the agentic pipeline to distributed outputs. Figure 2 details the state machine that governs this flow, with transition requirements that enforce workflow integrity.

Figure 1: System Architecture

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State transitions carry hard requirements. The transition function checks preconditions before allowing any transition. The system blocks transition from VALIDATING to GENERATING_AUDIO unless validation has passed. These gates exist in code, not documentation, making them impossible to accidentally bypass.

3.3 Transition Requirements

Transition	Requirement
SELECTING → RESEARCHING	Latin title set in source metadata
RESEARCHING → TRANSLATING	Research file path and completion timestamp exist
TRANSLATING → VALIDATING	Translation file path exists
VALIDATING → GENERATING_AUDIO	Validation passed
GENERATING_AUDIO → GENERATING_VIDEO	Audio file and completion timestamp exist
GENERATING_VIDEO → AWAITING_VIDEO	Video job start timestamp exists
AWAITING_VIDEO → DISTRIBUTING	Video file stable (size unchanged for 60 seconds)
DISTRIBUTING → PUBLISHING	Archive.org URL exists
PUBLISHING → REVIEW	YouTube video ID set, thumbnail uploaded
REVIEW → COMPLETE	Human approval timestamp exists

3.4 Agents and Tools

The pipeline orchestrates multiple AI systems and external services. Claude Code serves as the primary orchestration agent, reading instructions at session start and executing pipeline scripts. Other AI systems handle specialized tasks.

Figure 2: Pipeline State Machine

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Component	Role	Technology
Orchestrator	Reads state, runs scripts, manages transitions	Claude Code CLI
Deep Research	Generates scholarly context for each text	o3-deep-research via OpenRouter
Translation	Converts Latin to structured English JSON	Claude Sonnet 4.5 via OpenRouter
Text-to-Speech	Synthesizes audio narration	OpenAI TTS (tts-1-hd)
Cover Generation	Creates visual artwork for videos	DALL-E 3
Video Composition	Combines audio with synchronized Latin display	FFmpeg
Distribution	Uploads to Archive.org, commits to GitHub, generates blog	Python scripts + APIs
Publishing	Uploads video to YouTube (always as PRIVATE)	YouTube Data API v3

3.5 The Parking State Pattern

Video encoding takes 30 to 60 minutes, far too long for an interactive agent session. Rather than having the agent wait (wasting context and API costs), the pipeline implements a parking state.

When video composition starts, the system launches FFmpeg as a background process, records the job start timestamp, transitions to `AWAITING_VIDEO`, and ends the session with explicit resume instructions. The next session checks video stability by comparing file size across a 60-second window. If the file size has not changed, encoding is complete and the pipeline proceeds.

This pattern generalizes to any long-running operation. The agent is not a daemon; it starts and stops. Parking states acknowledge this constraint explicitly.

3.6 Translation Structure

The translation script produces structured JSON rather than plain text. The output contains two levels of structure. Metadata captures bibliographic information: volume, title (Latin and English), author, century, source, translator model, and known issues. Chunks represent semantic units of the text: chapter headings, body paragraphs, quotations, and dialogue. Each chunk includes the original Latin, English translation, section type, and speaker assignment.

```
{
  "metadata": {
    "volume_id": "PL170",
    "title": "Altercatio Monachi et Clerici",
```

```

"title_english": "Dispute Between a Monk and a Cleric",
"author": "Rupert of Deutz",
"century": "12th century",
"translator": "claude-sonnet-4.5",
"translation_date": "2025-06-17",
"estimated_duration_minutes": 28,
"known_issues": [
  "Source manuscript details unknown"
]
},
"chunks": [
  {
    "chunk_id": 1,
    "section_type": "chapter_heading",
    "speaker": "announcer",
    "latin": "ALTERCATIO MONACHI ET CLERICI",
    "english": "The Dispute Between a Monk and a Cleric"
  },
  {
    "chunk_id": 2,
    "section_type": "dialogue",
    "speaker": "monachus",
    "latin": "MONACHUS. Inique agis, resistens mihi...",
    "english": "The Monk speaks: You act unjustly..."
  }
]
}

```

This structure enables downstream automation. The audio generator uses speaker assignments to select TTS voices. The video composer uses chunk timing to synchronize Latin text display with narration. The blog generator preserves the semantic organization.

3.7 Video Composition

The composed video displays Latin text synchronized with English audio narration. The visual design is deliberately minimal: parchment-colored background, serif typography, centered Latin text that changes in sync with the spoken translation.

FFmpeg generates the video using a complex filter chain. The script loads actual audio timing from a timing JSON file produced during TTS synthesis, breaks Latin text into screen-sized chunks (approximately 65 characters per line, 6 lines per screen), calculates display duration for each chunk based on corresponding English audio duration, and generates FFmpeg drawtext filters with temporal enable clauses.

4. Deep Research as Metadata Foundation

4.1 The Deep Research Model

The pipeline uses deep research models via OpenRouter for scholarly context generation. Unlike standard language models that draw only from training data, deep research models perform actual web searches during inference. The API call includes a web search tool that allows the model to browse, read, and cite live web sources.

This distinction matters for the project’s epistemic claims. The research output contains URLs the model actually visited, not hallucinated citations that look plausible. When the output states that a text represents the first English translation of a particular work with a link to a university press page, that link exists and contains that claim.

4.2 Research Structure

The research prompt structures the request around five categories:

Section	Target Length	Content
Historical Context	400-600 words	Authorship, date, setting, intended audience
Theological/Intellectual Significance	400-600 words	Core themes, patristic context, influence
Manuscript Tradition and Editions	200-300 words	Key manuscripts, critical editions, existing translations
Author Biography	300-400 words	Life, major works, historical significance
Visual Resources	Variable	Wikimedia Commons images with URLs and licenses

The prompt emphasizes citation requirements: every factual claim must include a clickable URL. This instruction leverages the model’s web search capability, since it can only cite URLs it actually found.

4.3 Research as Blog Content

Deep research output flows into blog posts without AI rewriting. The blog generation script reads the research file and passes it through as the Analysis tab’s body content. This preserves the citation structure, typically over 100 URLs with text-highlight fragments pointing to specific passages on source pages.

A validation script confirms that published posts contain actual citations from the research file. The check catches cases where content was accidentally summarized or regenerated rather than preserved verbatim.

5. Outputs and Distribution

5.1 Output Channels

The pipeline distributes each completed translation across four platforms, each serving distinct access patterns.

YouTube hosts the primary output: audio narrations with synchronized Latin text display. Videos are always uploaded as private, reviewed by the human operator, then published. The video format serves listeners who prefer audio consumption, including commuters, people doing manual work, and those who find sustained reading difficult.

The blog at bibliothecarius-modernus.github.io provides the richest reading experience. Each post displays the deep research context (author background, historical setting, scholarly significance) alongside the translation itself. A tabbed interface presents three views: Analysis (deep research content), Translation (parallel Latin/English), and Resource Info (citations, downloads, metadata). The Translation tab offers three sub-views: side-by-side Latin/English, Latin only, or English only. Translation content loads dynamically from JSON files, with synchronized scrolling keeping Latin and English chunks aligned.

Archive.org receives permanent copies of audio files and translation JSON. This provides long-term preservation independent of YouTube’s platform policies and makes raw files available for anyone who wants to process them differently.

GitHub hosts two repositories: one containing translation JSON files organized by source collection, providing version-controlled access to structured translation data, and one powering the Jekyll blog.

5.2 Corpus Scope

The collection draws primarily from the *Patrologia Latina*, touching approximately 70 of its 221 volumes and representing roughly 100 distinct authors. Authors range from well-known figures (Augustine, Jerome, Gregory the Great) to deeply obscure ones (Magnus of Sens, Rupert of Deutz, Philip of Harveng). Content types include theological treatises, hagiographies, liturgical texts, polemical disputations, church council proceedings, cosmological speculation, and administrative correspondence.

Selection follows interest rather than a systematic plan. Some texts surface through deliberate searching (looking for untranslated works by a particular author or on a particular topic). Others emerge serendipitously while browsing the *Patrologia Latina*. Audience requests occasionally direct attention to specific texts.

5.3 Quality Mechanisms

Quality control operates through automated validation and human review rather than through scholarly apparatus.

Automated validation runs at multiple pipeline stages. Translation validation checks structural completeness: metadata fields present, chunks properly numbered, Latin and English both populated. Research validation confirms that blog posts contain actual citations from the deep research output. Description validation ensures YouTube metadata meets platform requirements.

The REVIEW state requires human approval before any video becomes public. The operator watches the rendered video, checks that audio and text synchronize correctly, verifies the description and thumbnail, and either approves publication or flags issues for correction.

Latin display provides ongoing accountability. Every video shows the original Latin alongside the English translation. The blog provides parallel display with numbered chunks for cross-referencing. Viewers with Latin reading ability can check the work. This transparency mechanism is passive rather than active; it enables verification but does not perform it automatically.

Provenance tracking prevents manual workarounds from corrupting the pipeline. Each artifact records which script produced it and when. Validation scripts check provenance, and downstream components depend on content being genuine rather than manually fabricated.

These mechanisms address structural errors and process integrity but do not directly detect semantic errors such as theological drift or anachronistic interpretation. The current ap-

proach relies on human review and the transparency of parallel Latin display. Automated semantic verification, discussed in Section 8, represents a natural future enhancement.

6. Publication Infrastructure

6.1 DOI Registration

Every text that reaches the blog receives a DOI through Zenodo. The implementation uses GitHub-Zenodo integration: pushing a GitHub release triggers a Zenodo webhook, which reads metadata and mints a DOI automatically.

The metadata follows Zenodo’s DataCite-based schema, including title, creators with ORCID identifiers, license (CC0), keywords, and related identifiers linking back to the blog, Archive.org, and GitHub. This creates a machine-readable link graph in the Zenodo metadata.

6.2 Metadata Standards

The blog implements schema.org as its primary external metadata standard, embedded via JSON-LD. Each post declares itself as a `ScholarlyArticle` with nested structures describing relationships: the original Latin work, the translation relationship, the original author, and the translator/editor.

For citation interchange, the Resource Info tab provides BibTeX and RIS export, allowing researchers to import citations directly into reference managers.

6.3 Platform Linking

Four platforms host project outputs, with linking relationships optimized for discovery and citation.

Every blog post links to its YouTube video (embedded player), Archive.org audio (download link), GitHub translation JSON (source data), and Zenodo DOI (canonical citation). Video descriptions follow a strict template including the blog URL, Archive.org download link, and GitHub repository link.

Zenodo serves as the hub where bidirectional linking is structural rather than optional. The DOI minting process embeds the blog post URL as a related identifier with “`isDocumentedBy`” relation. Archive.org and GitHub URLs appear as “`isSupplementedBy`” relations.

7. Agentic Workflow Principles

The project’s development surfaced principles that generalize beyond Latin translation to any workflow where agents execute multi-step tasks with human oversight.

7.1 State Over Instructions

Prose instructions are suggestions. State files are facts.

An agent can misinterpret “you should validate before proceeding” based on what it thinks validation means, whether it believes the current situation warrants an exception, or how it weighs stated preferences against its own judgment. It cannot misinterpret a state value.

The practical implementation: every session begins with the agent reading the state file. The file specifies current phase, accumulated artifacts, validation records, and next actions. The agent operates within those constraints rather than re-deriving them from first principles.

7.2 Gates Over Checklists

Checklists rely on the agent’s attention and memory. Gates are structural; they exist whether or not the agent remembers them.

Early pipeline versions included instructions like “remember to validate the translation before generating audio.” These worked most of the time. Most of the time is insufficient for production workflows. The current architecture implements gates as code: the transition function checks preconditions before allowing any state transition. The system refuses to proceed unless requirements are met.

A gate that prevents bad state transitions is worth more than any amount of instruction telling the agent to be careful.

7.3 The Helpful Bypass Problem

The most dangerous failure mode in agent orchestration is not capability failure. It is the agent’s instinct to work around problems.

When a pipeline script fails, the agent observes a gap between current state and desired outcome. Its training rewards helpfulness. The natural response is to fill the gap: create the missing file manually, synthesize the research from its own knowledge, proceed to the next stage. The pipeline appears to succeed.

But the quality guarantee is void. Research produced by deep research contains verified citations from actual web searches. Research the agent invents to bypass an API failure contains plausible-sounding but unverified claims. This failure mode is insidious because it masquerades as productivity.

The mitigation is structural: scripts fail loudly, gates check provenance (not just existence), and agent instructions explicitly prohibit working around failures.

7.4 Private-First Publishing

Agents will make mistakes. The question is whether those mistakes are visible before they become permanent.

Every external-facing action in the pipeline has a review buffer. YouTube uploads are set to PRIVATE, requiring human approval before publication. Blog posts can be inspected before deployment. The REVIEW state is not optional; it is where errors get caught.

The human’s job is not to supervise every step. The human’s job is to review outputs before they become permanent.

7.5 Templates Over Generation

When an agent generates formatted output, variation results. When an agent fills in a template, consistency results.

YouTube descriptions in the pipeline follow a strict template. The agent fills in title, author, volume, duration, and URLs. It does not compose prose about the text’s significance or invent framing language. The creative work happened once, when the template was designed. Execution is mechanical.

This applies wherever format consistency matters more than creative variation.

7.6 Summary

These principles reduce to a single insight: **constraints enable trust**. An agent operating within structural limits (state machines, validation gates, provenance checks) is an agent whose behavior can be predicted and verified. An agent operating on prose instructions and good intentions will eventually surprise you.

The goal is not to eliminate agent judgment. The goal is to channel it. Let agents exercise creativity within defined phases. Let them handle open-ended work they excel at. But for the connective tissue between phases, including transitions, validations, and publishing actions, remove judgment entirely. Make correct behavior structural.

8. Future Directions

8.1 Scope Considerations

The language constraint remains firm: only Latin texts. This reflects what can be done responsibly rather than what might be interesting to attempt.

Within the Latin constraint, scope questions remain genuinely open. The Patrologia Latina’s 1216 cutoff is Migne’s limitation, not the project’s. Later medieval Latin, Renaissance Latin, and Protestant Latin texts all represent natural extensions of the collection’s logic. The access problem applies equally regardless of period or confession.

Whether the governing principle is “patristic literature” (religious content) or “access problems in Latin” (the underlying mission) remains an open question. Medieval agricultural texts hold personal interest but would dilute the collection’s coherence. The boundary will likely remain fluid, guided by whether texts present access problems worth solving.

8.2 Automated Semantic Verification

The current quality mechanisms address structural errors and process integrity but do not directly detect semantic errors in translation. Two approaches merit future investigation.

Back-translation verification would use a separate model to translate the English output back into Latin, then compare the result against the original source. Significant semantic drift between original and back-translated Latin would flag potential mistranslation. This approach adds computational cost but provides a model-independent check.

LLM-as-judge evaluation would employ a model specifically prompted to identify theological anachronisms, doctrinal drift, or interpretive additions not present in the source. For patristic texts, this might flag translations that import post-Reformation theological vocabulary or concepts foreign to the original author’s context.

Neither approach eliminates the need for human review or the transparency of parallel Latin display. They would, however, provide an additional automated layer that could prioritize which translations warrant closer human attention.

8.3 Technology Trajectory

The project exists in a technological moment that will not last forever. AI translation capabilities improve continuously. The specific value proposition of AI-assisted translation may erode as tools become ubiquitous.

If translation becomes trivially easy, the access problem this project addresses will solve itself through other means. That would be success, not obsolescence. The project adds value precisely as long as the access barrier exists.

8.4 Sustainability

The project remains a personal endeavor with no plans for institutional transition. The pipeline is designed for single-operator sustainability: automated where automation helps, manually gated where human judgment matters, paced to match available attention and resources.

The CC0 designation reflects the intended legacy. Translations are released into the public domain without restriction. The project does not need to become an institution because outputs are free for institutions or individuals to adopt. The Zenodo DOI infrastructure ensures translations remain citable and discoverable independent of platform changes.

9. Conclusion

Bibliothecarius Modernus demonstrates that AI-assisted workflows can systematically address information access problems that traditional approaches have not solved at scale. The project has produced more than 200 translations since June 2024, making texts accessible that would otherwise remain locked behind Latin.

The technical contribution is not the AI translation itself; that capability exists widely. The contribution is the infrastructure that makes AI translation reliable, repeatable, and accountable: state machines that enforce workflow consistency, validation gates that catch errors before publication, provenance tracking that prevents quality shortcuts, and a publication pipeline that distributes outputs with persistent identifiers across multiple platforms.

The principles that emerged (state over instructions, gates over checklists, private-first publishing, templates over generation) apply to any agentic workflow where reliability matters more than capability. Constraints enable trust. Failures must be visible. Helpful bypasses are the enemy.

The measure of success is straightforward: someone who wants to read Rupert of Deutz, or Magnus of Sens, or Mappinius of Reims writing about parish hog purchases, can now do so when they could not before. Each text that crosses from inaccessible to accessible justifies the work, regardless of what happens afterward.

Acknowledgments

This project uses Claude (Anthropic) for translation and orchestration, OpenAI for text-to-speech synthesis and image generation, and various open-source tools including FFmpeg, Jekyll, and Python libraries. The Patrologia Latina source texts are available through Archive.org's digital collections.

Resources

- **YouTube Channel:** youtube.com/@BibliothecariusModernus
- **Blog:** bibliothecarius-modernus.github.io
- **GitHub (Translations):** github.com/wryan14/Latin-Patristic-Texts

- **GitHub (Blog):** github.com/bibliothecarius-modernus/bibliothecarius-modernus.github.io
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